

SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF PHRASES IN TRANSLATED WORKS**Babadjanov Mansurbek Kurbanboyevich**

Ph.D. (PhD), associate professor

Karakalpak State University

Mominova Yulduz Aminboyevna

teacher of Tashkent University of Humanities

Annotation: The article talks about the use of phrases in Uzbek-Karakalpak translated works.

Key words: phraseologism, phrase, expression

Nowadays the growing prestige of the Uzbek and Karakalpak languages as the state languages, the expansion of their functional and stylistic capabilities, and the translation of works created in these languages from one to the other, make it necessary to study expressions in both languages on a comparative basis.

Comparative study of languages is one of the the factor of formation and development for linguistics.

Comparative analysis of the language of works translated from relative languages is important in linguistics.

The language of poetic and prose works created in Uzbek linguistics has been sufficiently studied. A lot of works has been done on the works of many poets and writers, as well as on the language of fiction. However, no matter how many works of mutual translation from relative Turkic languages there are, little attention has been paid to their linguistic study.

Every writer has their own way of using phrasal verbs. If translating a work created in a certain language into another language, in particular, in the process of turning phrases, alternatives available in the language are also used. This, in turn, requires skill and knowledge from the translator, and requires that he has fully mastered the features and rules of both languages. In addition, it is necessary to be familiar with the culture, national values, and living conditions of these peoples. Because any phrase is directly related to the lifestyle and national culture of that people. It takes great skill from the translator to find the available alternative in their translation.

Phrases of relative languages have their own alternatives, which mean the same thing but have different lexical composition. Finding and applying them correctly in translation will give a

positive result to achieve the intended goal. From this point of view, we observed that the Uzbek language phrases are expressed in the translation with the unique Karakalpak language phrases.

In the work "Starry Nights" there is a phrase "*bir tan-birjonbo'lmoq*". Phraseme means "to be united". The writer used this phrase in the work as follows: -agar *bir tan-birjonbo'lib*, Boburmirezogaxizmatqilsak, hammamizomonqolurmiz, hechqaysimizningbirmo'yimizkambo'lmag'ay(48). The interpreter translated the quoted passage from the original as follows: *Yegerbirjeñnenqol, birjağadan bas shīğarīp* Babīrmīrzağaxīzmetyetsek, hōmmemizinshaalla, amanqalarmīz! (50)

The phrase "*bir tan-birjonbo'lmoq*" is correctly reflected by the alternative "*birjeñnenqolbirjağadan basshīğariw*". Although the expressions are based on different images in both languages, they have semantic commonality. From this point of view, their usage in the translation process gives the expected result. Taking this into account, these idioms are called alternative idioms.

In another example in the work, the phrase *ko'nglitaskintopmoqis* used as "to be calm, to calm down". The writer used this phrase in the work as follows: *Fuqarotaxtvorisiniko'rsin, ko'nglitaskintopsin* (50).

The translator also used the phrase in the translation with its own alternative: *Puxarataxtmiyrasxorīnkørsin, kewilleriqarartapsīn* (52). In the Karakalpak language, the phrase "*kewliqarartabīw*" is used in the same way as in Uzbek in the sense of "to calm down". A comparison shows that this phrase is different in form, but has the same meaning. Overall, the Uzbek phrase is reflected in the Karakalpak translation.

In particular, phrases translated with such a lexical alternative can be observed in the original copy of R. Fayzi's works "HazratiInson" and its translation into Karakalpak. In the Karakalpak translation of the phrases used in the writer's work, there are many unique phrases of the Karakalpak language. For example, *Xayrlashib, eshigigakirarkan, "haliyamdunyonisuvolsato'pig'igachiqmaydi-ya... man nimanigapirdimu, u nimalarnio'ylavotti", deyag'ijinibqo'ydi*(15). In Uzbek, this phrase means "the careless one who passed away". The translator gave the Uzbek phrase with its Karakalpak alternative and clarified its meaning very correctly: "*Xoshlasīpyesiginekiripbaratīryp, "dunyanīsuwalsa, uyrekkebirpul", - depoyladī, men ne deymen, qobīzīm ne deydi?! (11).*" Even if the form of phrases expressing the same meaning matches exactly, the words forming the basis of the combination are different or the basic reality matches. The internal semantics of such phrases are the same or close to each other. Therefore, it is possible to use one of them instead of the other or give it in translation. Because such phrases are alternatives that can replace each other.

In Uzbek, the phrase “*ko‘ztikmoq*”, related to the word *ko‘z*, is used in the sense of "staring". In our opinion, the writer inappropriately used this phrase in the text of "HazratiInson": *Xatimniko‘ztikibkutgansiz, bilaman* (79). It can be seen from the text that the meaning understood from the phrase does not correspond to the meaning of the text. The reason is that the text expresses the meaning of 'waiting and waiting impatiently'. In the dictionary of Sh. Rakhmatullaev, the phrase "to stare" is recorded.

The translator corrected this mistake and translated the text as follows: *Xatimdi koziñ tort bolip kutip otirg’anindī bilemen* (67). This is where the skill of the translator was shown. The meaning that was not understood in the original is fully reflected in the translation.

In the process of translation, translating the content of the text into another language, including lexemes and their meanings, requires a lot of work and skill from the translator. In particular, the wrong translation of phrases can damage the artistic value of the text in every way. It is natural to cause uncertainty and misunderstanding in thought.

It is observed this situation in the translation of the work "HazratiInson". In some places of the translation of the work, the meaning of the phrase in the original is wrongly translated. For example, *Bu shunday og‘ir sukunat ediki, pashsha uchgani yoqmasdi, yuraklarga qil sig‘masdi* (28). In our opinion, the writer used the phrase more incorrectly in the text. In the phraseological dictionary of the Uzbek language, the phrase **yuragiga qil sig‘maydi** is recorded in the meaning of “being very depressed, mentally crushed, not being able to do anything”. The interpreter translated this text as follows: *Bul sonday awir tinshiliq yedi, shibinnin izildisi jaqpay, sirkeleri suw koteriey qaldi* (23). The mistake in the Uzbek text was repeated in the Karakalpak translation in the same way. In the explanatory dictionary of the Karakalpak language, the phrase "sirkesi suw kotermew" is recorded as meaning "not liking anything", and in the phraseological dictionary of the Uzbek language, it is explained as "absolutely not tolerating criticism". From the above points, it can be concluded that this phrase is used incorrectly in both languages.

As a conclusion, it can be said that in the translation of an artistic work, the translator must first of all absorb the meaning of the original work into the translation. Otherwise, wrongly turned phrases will have a negative effect on the whole text and spoil its original meaning. Therefore, the correct translation of phrases is an important factor to further increase the value of the work.

REFERENCES:

- Раҳматуллаев Ш. Ўзбек тилининг изоҳли фразеологик луғати.–Тошкент.1978.;
- Раҳматуллаев Ш. Ўзбек тилининг фразеологик луғати. –Тошкент.1992.

Ешбаев Ж. Қарақалпақ тилинің қысқаша фразеологиялық сөзлігі. –Нукус. 1985
Файзий, Р. Ҳазрати инсон. –Тошкент. 1978.; Қодиров П. Юлдузли тунлар. –Тошкент.
2012.

Kurbanbaevich, B. M. (2019). THE PHRASEMES TRANSLATED WITH THE DESCRIPTION METHOD IN THE UZBEK-KARAKALPAK LITERARY WORKS. *ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies*, 8(6), 20-26.

Kilichov, N. R., & Durdon, A. (2022). Vocabulary in the old turkish language.

Rakhmonov, N., Kurbaniyazov, M., & Kilichov, N. (2020, December). SOME NOTES ABOUT CLASSIC POETICS. In Конференции.

Radjabbaevich, K. N. (2019). LINGUOAESTHETIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE LEXICS OF MONUMENT "OLTUN YORUG". *ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies*, 8(6), 35-42.

Киличов, Н. Р. (2019). ЗАЙМСТВОВАННАЯ ЛЕКСИКА В ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИИ "ЗОЛОТОЙ БЛЕСК" ("АЛТУН ЯРУК"). In ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКЕ (pp. 34-38).

Киличов, Н. (2022). Қадимги туркий тилдаги синоним компонентли жуфт отлар семантикаси. Развитие лингвистики и литературоведения и образовательных технологий в эпоху глобализации, 1(1), 40-43.

Киличов, Н. Р. ҚАДИМГИ ТУРКИЙ ТИЛДАГИ СИНОНИМ КОМПОНЕНТЛИ ЖУФТ ОТЛАР СЕМАНТИКАСИ («Олтун ёруғ» асари мисолида).

ABDULLAYEV, S. FRAZELOGIZMLAR-MUHIM TIL BIRLIGI SIFATIDA. *АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ НАУЧНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ МИРЕ Учредители: Общественная организация "Институт социальной трансформации"*, 19-21.

Abdullayev, S., & Abdullayev, O. (2023). O‘ZBEK VA QORAQALPOQ TILLARIDA IQTISODIYOT SOHASIGA DOIR ZAMONAVIY LEKSIKA. *Talqin Va Tadqiqotlar*, 1(31).

Абдуллаев, С. (2023). Структурно-семантические особенности пословиц в узбекском и каракалпакском языках. *Американский журнал языка, грамотности и обучения в области STEM-образования (2993–2769)*, 1 (9), 70–73.

Radjabbaevich, K. N., Allambergenovich, K. M., Dauletbaevich, A. S., Adilbayevna, K. Z., & Gulmanovna, Y. N. (2023). The Dialectal Structure of the Work "Oltun Yorug". *Telematique*, 7739-7744.

Kurbaniyazov, MakhsudAllambergenovich. "THE DIVERSITY OF THE THEME IN THE RABGHUZIY'S STORY." *Культурология, искусствоведение и филология: современные взгляды и научные исследования*. 2018. 56-59.

Ibragimova, Z., & Ibragimova, U. (2020). PROFESSIONAL WORDS IN THE UZBEK DIALECTS OF KARAKALPAKSTAN WHICH CAN BE FOUND IN OTHER UZBEK DIALECTS. In *Recent Scientific Investigation* (pp. 69-72).

Ibragimova, Z. (2023). FORMATION OF SOCIAL COMPETENCE STUDENTS ON FOREIGN LANGUAGE LESSONS. *Science and innovation*, 2(B6), 48-52.

Abdullayev, D. A. (2020). «O 'ZBEK TILINING IZOHLI LUG 'ATI» DA IBORALARNING IZOHLANISH TAMOYILLARI. *Интернаука*, (40-2), 48-50.

Davronbek, A., & Dilfuza, K. (2023). FRAZELOGIZMLARDA GRAMMATIK ME'YOR VA IJODIY QONUNIYATLARNING BIRIKUV USULLARI. *BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI*, 3(11), 91-94.

Abdullayev Davronbek. (2023). NUTQNING IJODIY VOQELANISHIDA LUG'AVIY BIRLIKLAR VAZIFADOSHLIGI. *Scientific Impulse*, 2(13), 63–67.

MASHARIPOVNA, R. K. Formation Of Correct Writing Skills. *JournalNX*, 7(02), 206-210.

Masharipovna, R. K. (2021). THE IMPORTANCE OF DICTIONARIES IN INCREASING LITERACY. *Conferencious Online*, 25-27.

Masharipovna, R. K. (2022, October). TAYANCH KOMPETENSIYALARNI SHAKLLANTIRISH ORQALI ONA TILI DARSLARINING SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH. In *Proceedings of Scientific Conference on Multidisciplinary Studies* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 219-222).

Yuldashevich, O. E. (2023). The Place of Arabic Changes Related to Islam in the Linguistic Landscape of the Turkish People. *Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture*, 4(7), 83-86.

Orazbaev Ergash Yuldashevich (2021). Globallashuv davrida ona tili fanining ahamiyati. *Евразийский научный журнал*, (4), 18-19.

Nurjanov, O. Ethnographisms Denoting Children's Games. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 4(1), 126-128.

Нуржанов О.Е., Абдримова К.С., Бободжонова Ю.И. КРАСОТА ЛЕКСИЧЕСКИХ ВЫРАЖЕННЫХ СРЕДСТВ, ИСПОЛЬЗУЕМЫХ В РОМАНЕ "TESS OF D'URBERVILLES" THOMAS HARDY [BEAUTY OF LEXICAL EXPRESSED MEANS USED IN THE NOVEL "TESS OF THE D'URBERVILLES" BY THOMAS HARDY] // VII

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC REVIEW OF THE PROBLEMS OF HISTORY,
CULTURAL STUDIES AND PHILOLOGY

Yuldashev, O. (2023). A LOOK AT THE STUDY OF FOLK PROVERBS. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(10), 47-50.

Ashirov, O. (2023). “MUQADIMAT UL-ADAB” QIPCHOQ LAHJASIGA OID QAYDLAR AKS ETGAN MUMTOZ MANBA. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 3(9), 164-167.

Ashirov, O. (2023). BADIY MATNLARDA NUTQIY AKT NAZARIYASIGA DOIR BA’ZI MULOHAZALAR. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 2(10), 27-29.

Allambergenova, M. (2021). O‘RXUN-ENASOY OBIDALARINING O‘ZBEKISTONDA O‘RGANILISHI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(4), 20-24.